

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS AND SIMULATION OF BIMORPH MACRO-FIBER COMPOSITE UNDERGOING LARGE DISPLACEMENTS AND ROTATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Because of its direct and converse piezoelectric effect, the piezoelectric smart structures especially bonded with macro-fiber composite (MFC), which is more flexible, reliable and has stronger activating forces, can be widely used. But the complication of the structure of MFC takes difficulties into the modelling of the piezoelectric smart structures. The paper develops a electromechanical coupled geometrically nonlinear finite element model for thin-walled composite structures based on Reissner-Mindlin plate theory and large rotation nonlinear theory (LRT56). And also, the model considers the various fiber angles of the structures. The model is first validated by a MFC bonded cantilever beam, and then is analysed by a laminated bimorph plates bonded with MFC-d31.

1 INTRODUCTION

Combined with piezoelectric materials, such normal structures are called as piezoelectric smart structures. Because of its direct and converse piezoelectric effect, which makes it can be self-sensing and self-controlling, the piezoelectric smart structures can be widely used for vibration control, shape control, health monitoring, energy harvesting and so on[1-3]. Therefore, an accurate model for these piezoelectric smart structures is quite necessary.

Among different types of piezoelectric materials, the macro-fiber composite (MFC) should be widest used and researched on account of the high flexibility, reliability and strong activating forces., which is first invented by NASA Langley Research Center[4]. And according to the direction of polarization, there are two types of MFCs named as MFC-d31 and MFC-d33 which are dominated by d31 effect and d33 effect respectively. MFC is made of several different kinds of materials and has complex structure. It is mainly consist of central active layer, electrode layers and outermost polyimide film protective layers on the both sides. The active layer consists of rectangular piezoelectric ceramic fibers intermittently embedded in the epoxy matrix, and the electrodes in the electrode layer are cross-aligned. The complexity of the structure makes it difficult to build models of such structures bonded with MFC.

In available literatures, they mostly talk about linear modelling. Assuming that the potential is linear in the thickness direction of the structure, Panda & Ray[5] and Varelis & Saravanos[6] develop Von Karman nonlinear finite element model but just for moderate deformation and small rotation. Lentzen et al[7] develop a moderate rotation nonlinear model of piezoelectric laminated structures. Kundu et al[8] and Dash & Singh[9] develop a full geometrically nonlinear model based on the Reissner-Mindlin hypothesis. And Zhang et al[10-12] develop a large rotation nonlinear model.

Based on our previous research[13], a electromechanical coupling geometrically nonlinear finite element model considering all parts of MFC(piezoceramic fibers as active part and epoxy matrix, electrode layers as non-active part) is proposed based on Reissner-Mindlin plate theory and large rotation nonlinear theory (LRT56). And various piezo-fiber orientations are also considered. To validate the proposed model, a piezoelectric cantilever beam is simulated. And then, a bimorph structure is simulated for the influence of various fiber angles.

2 MATHEMATICAL MODELING

2.1 Constitutive equations

Because of the complex composition and structure, MFC is equivalent to orthotropic material with piezo fiber angles by homogenization method[14]. And considering the laminated structures with different angles among several layers (shown in Fig.1), the coordinate system of piezo fibers should be introduced and the constitutive equation in this coordinate is

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{c}^E \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \boldsymbol{e}^T \boldsymbol{E}, \quad (1)$$

$$\boldsymbol{D} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} + \boldsymbol{\chi}^S \boldsymbol{E}, \quad (2)$$

where the \square means in the coordinate system of piezo fibers. In the equation, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ represent stress and strain, as well as \boldsymbol{D} , \boldsymbol{E} , \boldsymbol{c} , \boldsymbol{e} and $\boldsymbol{\chi}$ represent electric displacement vector, electric field vector, the elastic constant matrix, the piezoelectric constant matrix and the dielectric constant matrix respectively.

Fig.1. Multi-layer composites with MFCs

For the modeling and calculation, it is needed to transfer the constitutive equations to the structural coordinate system

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{c} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \boldsymbol{e}^T \boldsymbol{E}, \quad (3)$$

$$\boldsymbol{D} = \boldsymbol{e} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} + \boldsymbol{\chi} \boldsymbol{E}, \quad (4)$$

where

$$\boldsymbol{c} = \boldsymbol{T}^T \boldsymbol{c}^E \boldsymbol{T}, \quad \boldsymbol{e} = \boldsymbol{e}^T \boldsymbol{T}, \quad \boldsymbol{\chi} = \boldsymbol{\chi}^S. \quad (5)$$

2.2 Nonlinear modeling

The deformation of arbitrary point in the structure can be expressed as

$$v_\alpha^0 = v_\alpha^1 + \Theta^3 v_\alpha^2, \quad (6)$$

$$v_3^0 = v_3^1 + \Theta^3 v_3^2, \quad (7)$$

where v_α^0 and v_3^0 represent displacement of mid-surface as well as v_α^1 and v_3^1 represent the rotation. In many literatures, v_3^1 is just neglected. And Green-Lagrange strain tensor with full geometric nonlinearities is obtained by considering unchangeable thickness and FOSD[12,13]

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\alpha\beta}^0 = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\alpha\beta}^1 + \Theta^3 \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\alpha\beta}^2 + (\Theta^3)^2 \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\alpha\beta}^3, \quad (8)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\alpha 3}^0 = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\alpha 3}^1 \quad (9)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\alpha\beta}$, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\alpha 3}$ and Θ^3 represent the in-plane shear strains, transverse shear strains and distance in the thickness direction respectively. Considering all degree of freedom of

$v_\alpha^0, v_3^0, v_\alpha^1$ and v_3^1 , the strain-displacement relationships of LRT56 can be obtained.

Using principle of virtual work

$$\delta W_{\text{int}} - \delta W_{\text{ext}} = 0 \quad (10)$$

where W_{int} is internal virtual work and W_{ext} is external virtual work, and formulating these virtual works

$$\begin{aligned} {}^{t+\Delta t} \delta W_{\text{int}} &= \int_V ({}^{t+\Delta t} \delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon})^T ({}^{t+\Delta t} \boldsymbol{\sigma}) - ({}^{t+\Delta t} \delta \mathbf{E})^T ({}^{t+\Delta t} \mathbf{D}) dV \\ &= \delta \Delta \mathbf{q}^T ({}^t \mathbf{K}_{uu} \Delta \mathbf{q} + {}^t \mathbf{K}_{u\phi} \Delta \boldsymbol{\phi} + {}^t \mathbf{F}_{ui}) \\ &\quad + \delta \Delta \boldsymbol{\phi}^T ({}^t \mathbf{K}_{\phi u} \Delta \mathbf{q} + {}^t \mathbf{K}_{\phi\phi} \Delta \boldsymbol{\phi} + {}^t \mathbf{G}_{\phi i}) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

$$\begin{aligned} {}^{t+\Delta t} \delta W_{\text{ext}} &= \int_V \delta \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{f}_b dV + \int_{\Omega} \delta \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{f}_s d\Omega + \delta \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{f}_c \\ &\quad - \int_{\Omega} \delta \boldsymbol{\phi}^T \mathbf{Q} d\Omega - \delta \boldsymbol{\phi}^T \mathbf{Q}_c \\ &= \delta \Delta \mathbf{q}^T \mathbf{F}_{ue} + \delta \Delta \boldsymbol{\phi}^T \mathbf{G}_{\phi e} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

the nonlinear model of static equation can be obtained

$$\mathbf{K}_{uu} \mathbf{q} + \mathbf{K}_{u\phi} \boldsymbol{\Phi}_a = \mathbf{F}_{ue} \quad (13)$$

where \mathbf{K}_{uu} , $\mathbf{K}_{u\phi}$, \mathbf{q} , $\boldsymbol{\Phi}_a$ and \mathbf{F}_{ue} are the elastic stiffness matrix, the piezoelectric coupled stiffness matrix, the nodal displacement vector, the actuation voltage vector and the external force vector.

3 NUMERICAL SIMULATION

3.1 Validation of model

Firstly, the proposed model is validated by a MFC bonded cantilevered beam, which is first presented by Wang et al[15]. The structure is shown in fig.2 that the host structure is made of aluminium and MFC-d33 is bonded on the both surfaces with a distance of 15mm from the stiff end. The Young modulus and Poisson's ratio of aluminium are $Y=70\text{GPa}$ and $\nu=0.32$. And material properties of the protective layers made of polyimide film are $Y=2.8\text{GPa}$ and $\nu=0.3$ respectively. The material properties of the active part of MFC-d33 made of piezoelectric materials can be found in Table 1.

Fig. 2. Schematic figure of the MFC bonded cantilever beam

Table 1. Material properties

MFC-d33
$\tilde{Y}_3 = 29.4\text{GPa}$
$\tilde{Y}_2 = \tilde{Y}_1 = 15.2\text{GPa}$
$\tilde{G}_{32} = \tilde{G}_{31} = 6.06\text{GPa}$
$\tilde{G}_{21} = 5.79\text{GPa}$
$\tilde{\nu}_{32} = \tilde{\nu}_{31} = 0.312$

$$\tilde{\nu}_{21} = 0.312$$

$$\tilde{d}_{33} = 467 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m/V}$$

$$\tilde{d}_{32} = -210 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m/V}$$

$$h_E = 0.5 \text{ mm}$$

Applying voltages of 400V to the MFC-d33 on the top surface and calculated by the proposed model, the results are just gotten shown in Fig.3. Compared to the experimental and simulated results from other literatures, it is clear that the deformation from the proposed model is quiet approximate with the literature results.

Fig.3. Central line displacement of the MFC bonded smart plate

3.2 bimorph MFC

At this part, the model is analyzed by a laminated bimorph plates with MFC-d33. The structure is comprised of two MFC-d33 with opposite polarization direction and clamped by the left side, which is shown in Fig.4. And also the material properties of MFC-d33 can be found in Table 1. A 9×8 mesh with rectangular elements fitted for the different parts is used for the finite element analysis.

Fig.4. Schematic figure of bimorph and finite element mesh

Applying voltage of 800V and -800V to the top MFC and bottom MFC respectively, which means the electric field along the MFC is 1600V/mm because the distance between two electrodes of MFC-d33 is $h_E=0.5\text{mm}$, the structure produces large deformations. And when the angle between fibers of two layers changes, the deformations are very different due to various piezo fiber angles, which are shown in fig. 4. There are six different angles from 0° to 90° for simulation and it can be observed that the largest deformation happens at 0° (fibers along lengthwise direction) and the smallest happens at 90° , and the largest twisting happens at 45° .

Fig. 11. Surface shapes of the bimorph with MFC-d33 patches having different fiber angles

There are two types of results shown in the figure. The shape in blue line is calculated by the linear model and the colorful one is simulated by the proposed nonlinear model with LRT56. It can be observed that when the linear model cannot describe the deformation accurately when the large deformation occurs, and it even does worse when large rotation occurs. But calculated by the proposed nonlinear model, it can be better to describe the large displacement and rotation.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The paper developed a nonlinear finite element model for laminated piezoelectric smart structures, based on Reissner-Mindlin plate theory and large rotation nonlinear theory and considered the influence of the various piezo fiber angles.

The proposed model has been validated by a piezoelectric cantilevered beam which is bonded with MFC-d33 on both sides. And then there was another numerical example of bimorph MFC to analyse the different results between the proposed nonlinear model and linear model which showed the higher veracity especially for the condition of large displacement and rotation. The influence of various fiber angles was also analysed by this example and the results showed that if the angle between fiber direction and lengthwise direction is smaller, the larger displacement will occur but opposite for twisting.

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